

1 **Expression of inflammatory markers in B-lymphocytes of humans with multiple sclerosis.**

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6 We measured total transcription in B-cells isolated from patients with the CNS inflammatory disease,
7 multiple sclerosis. B-cells isolated based on CD19+ expression were enriched for expression of CD27,
8 CD38 and CD300A, and depleted for expression of CD247, CD40 and CD5. B lymphocytes from patients
9 with multiple sclerosis expressed high levels of chemokine receptors CCR2, CCR9 and CCR10. Aryl
10 hydrocarbon receptor expression (AHR) was lost, with concomitant induction of the aryl hydrocarbon
11 receptor repressor (AHRR); this was accompanied by induction of exhaustion markers CTLA4, PD1
12 (CD274) and TIGIT. Moderately high expression of inflammasome cytokine interleukin-1beta (IL1B) was
13 measured together with loss of the alpha subunit of the interleukin-12 cytokine (IL12A), with induction of
14 caspase-10. We describe here induction of a group of immunoglobulin-like receptors in multiple sclerosis
15 on the B-lymphocyte, including LILRB4, LILRA1, ILDR1, BIVM and VSIG2, with reduced expression of
16 IGSF9. We present here a complete description of the B-lymphocyte inflammatory and immune activation
17 state in a CNS inflammatory disease that results in significant morbidity.
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Results

We measured total transcription in human B cells from patients with multiple sclerosis using RNA-sequencing (published) of CD19-enriched B-lymphocytes to characterize their cellular identity, gain insight into their functional capacities and blindly describe extent of cellular pathology.

Figure 1: B-cells from humans with multiple sclerosis express CD27, CD38 and CD300A.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
939	1.99E-04	0.257	-3.720048	-0.9561196	454.89	CD27	554/	96.8
952	2.25E-04	0.3702	-3.688719	-1.3657138	589.12	CD38	568/	96.7
11314	5.51E-03	0.3063	-2.775389	-0.850036	82.55	CD300A	1795/17129	89.5

Figure 2: B-cells from humans with multiple sclerosis are depleted for expression of CD247, CD40 and CD5.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
919	8.90E-03	0.22	2.615822	0.5754564	84.53	CD247	2140/	87.5
958	2.36E-04	0.129	3.677474	0.4745492	1631.34	CD40	587/	96.6
921	6.82E-03	0.2572	2.705588	0.6959253	141.58	CD5	1955/	88.6

Figure 3: High expression of chemokine receptors CCR2, CCR9 and CCR10 in MS.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
729230	7.48E-05	0.6161	-3.960576	-2.4402079	38.71	CCR2	383/	97.8
10803	3.20E-04	0.4249	-3.598849	-1.5291623	74.21	CCR9	661/	96.1
2826	4.00E-02	0.3879	-2.053598	-0.7965096	17.49	CCR10	3821/	77.7

We observed activation of chemokine receptors CCR2 and CCR9 (**Figure 3**). Tolerogenic mechanisms help establish homeostasis in the immune system, the basis of which underlies loss of immune control in MS and other autoimmune/inflammatory diseases. We found significant modulation of the aryl hydrocarbon system in the B-lymphocytes of humans with MS (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Aryl hydrocarbon receptor expression (AHR) system modulation.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
57491	1.64E-03	0.1593	-3.147974	-0.5014352	54.05	AHRR	1140/	93.3
196	7.68E-03	0.1842	2.66563	0.4908987	452.85	AHR	2038/	88.1

While the AHR repression AHRR was activated, AHR was silenced, indicating loss of AHR tolerogenic mechanisms in the MS B-lymphocyte. We continued our study of tolerogenic mechanisms in immunity relating to precise immune control by studying expression of surface receptors that function in the exhaustion program at the B-cell immunological synapse (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5: Induction of exhaustion markers on the multiple sclerosis B-lymphocyte.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
29126	3.00E-03	0.3282	-2.967531	-0.9738329	30.71	CD274	1409/	91.8
1493	6.27E-02	0.4724	-1.861029	-0.8791462	13.3	CTLA4	4606/	73.1
201633	2.15E-02	0.1451	-2.299296	-0.3336252	310.32	TIGIT	3024/	82.3

Exhaustion marker PD-1 (CD274) was activated, as was CTLA4 but to a less significant extent. the T cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM domains, *TIGIT*, was also activated in the MS B-cell. We next measured innate immune caspase and inflammasome activity (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6: Caspase-10 inflammasome activity in multiple sclerosis.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3553	2.06E-02	0.403	-2.315143	-0.9331004	134.71	IL1B	2967/	82.7
3592	2.73E-02	0.2263	2.207869	0.4995905	81.15	IL12A	3298/	80.7
843	2.01E-04	0.1873	-3.717568	-0.6963308	783.76	CASP10	557/	96.7

Moderately high expression of inflammasome cytokine interleukin-1beta (IL1B) was measured together with loss of the alpha subunit of the interleukin-12 cytokine (IL12A), with induction of caspase-10.

Finally, we also studied expression of a group of immunoglobulin-like receptors on the B-lymphocyte whose complete set of functions in immunity is not yet completely understood (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7: Activation of a group of immunoglobulin-like receptors in multiple sclerosis on the B-lymphocyte.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
11006	1.93E-08	0.3529	-5.618326	-1.9825636	94.99	LILRB4	16/	99.9
11024	2.54E-04	0.3783	-3.658658	-1.384102	16.33	LILRA1	612/	96.4
286676	4.38E-04	0.2884	-3.516058	-1.0141081	73.65	ILDR1	732/	95.7
54841	2.48E-03	0.2436	-3.026363	-0.7370709	42.66	BIVM	1316/	92.3
23584	6.92E-03	0.4216	-2.700635	-1.1386577	15.2	VSIG2	1967/	88.5
57549	1.35E-02	0.4313	2.470377	1.0653817	32.35	IGSF9	2520/17129	85.3

Discussion

We presented here a complete description of the B-lymphocyte inflammatory and immune activation state in a CNS inflammatory disease that results in significant morbidity.